

USE OF BORROWED WORDS IN ENGLISH

Ashurova Zamira Vakhobovna

English teacher of Rishton District Vocational School No. 2

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of loanwords at the language level, their subjection to the laws of their own strata, and the use of loanwords in English.

Key words: acquisition, own layer, lexical-semantic system of the language, main signs of acquisition, thematic groups.

A word adopted from a foreign language, i.e. borrowed words, is a result of enrichment of the vocabulary based on an external source. N. Mahmudov stated that in different periods of historical development, as a natural result of different levels of contacts between different, far-off peoples, a certain number of words were more or less transferred from one language of these peoples to another [4, 7]. The main signs of appropriation are its long-term use in individual and collective speech, its subordination to the laws of its own stratum, its absorption into the lexical-semantic system of the language, and its adaptation to practical writing [1,79].

The current vocabulary of the Uzbek language is a phenomenon formed during the entire historical development of the Uzbek language. The period of appearance and origin of the words in it are also different [6,120].

One of the linguists who carried out a number of theoretical and practical works on the comparative study of the English and Uzbek languages is J. Boranov. Thematic group of acquisitions, as English acquisitions are in lexical-semantic relations such as synonymy and antonymy, they are combined into thematic groups together with members of a specific paradigm. Such thematic groups have their place in the language based on hierarchical (level) relations.

Since the vocabulary of the language is developing in line with the changes in the society, the importance of native words in the enrichment of the lexicon is great [2, 45].

After independence, the direct assimilation of a number of lexemes from foreign languages into our language increased. In particular, learning English is of great importance. English words adapted to the Uzbek language can be studied by dividing them into socio-political, economic, cultural-educational and sports thematic groups. English lexemes related to the thematic group of the sports field have been acquired so much after independence that it is convenient and appropriate to study them systematically, separating them from the words of the

cultural and educational field. Currently, most of these words are actively used in spoken and written speech as words of their own class. English acquisitions can be studied by classifying them based on the following thematic groups:

1. Vocabulary related to the socio-political sphere.
2. Vocabulary related to the field of science
3. Vocabulary related to the economic field.
4. Lexicon related to the cultural and educational sphere.
5. Vocabulary related to sports.

Today, many borrowings that are not yet recorded in our dictionaries are used in the press pages. In particular, many lexemes used in the field of information technology do not have recommended variants in Uzbek dictionaries [3, 26-27]. In our opinion, if necessary, they should be Uzbekized in accordance with the nature of our language and included in our dictionaries. We learn by classifying based on lines.

1. Names of food products: *bifshteks, gamburger, yogurt, keks, ketchup, jemr.*
2. Names of Drinks: *kokteyl, koka-kola, pepsi-kola, pom, viski.*
3. Clothing names: *jemper, jinsi, kovboyka, pidjak, pijama, sviter, trusi, raglan.*
4. Name of household goods: *mikser, pleyer//pleyyer.*
5. Names of cosmetics and household goods: *sheyping, shampun, fen, servis.*
6. Names signifying the concept of place: *vokzal, dendropark, drenaj, skver, kemping, klub, kollej, kottej, motel, bar (kichikrestoran, mayxona), tunnel, zoopark, xoll park, supermarket .*
7. Material names: *belting, tik, reps, sheviot, neylon, koverkot .*
8. Names of transport vehicles: *trolleybus, ekspress, tramvay, pikap, layner, treyler, tanker.*

Acquisitions related to the field of science can be studied in the following groups [5, 14]: fields of science, names of directions: logistics, ufology, management, etc.

Here are examples of adaptations related to some fields of science:

Ethnographic appropriation: totem, totemism, etc.

Drawing skills: like a watman.

Hydraulic slang: like a pier.

Appropriations related to worldview, theory and socio-political sphere: formalism, centrism, trade unionism, dominion, impeachment, lockout, summit, centrist, laborist, leader, rally, speaker, charter, boycott, etc.

Appropriations related to the economic sphere and trade: leasing, export, banknote, broker, warrant, voucher, grant, dumping, dealer, discount, import,

importer, investor, barter, budget, marketing, manager, holding, clearing, consulting, bartender, businessman, business, etc.

Sports adjectives: out, outsider, badminton, businessman, basketball, table tennis, water polo, bicycle track, kart, karting, court, match, motorball, leader, motocross, knockout, knockdown, round, rugby, record, record holder, ring, set, speedway, sport, sprint, sprinter, start, time-out, tennis, track, trainer, training, final, finish, football, hockey, championship, yacht sport boat, yachtsman, bullit, boots, volleyball, handball, games, etc.

As a conclusion, it is worth noting that in the process of word assimilation before independence, it is possible to observe that some lexemes were adapted to the phonetic, lexical, morphological or syntactic phenomena of the Russian language and were assimilated into the lexicon of the Uzbek language.

References:

1. Azizov A. Tilshunoslikkakashirish. -Toshkent, 1963.
2. Boboxonova L. Ingliztilististikasi. -Toshkent, 1993.
3. Gachicheladze G. Problemrealichekogoperevoda. Avtoref. dokt. diss. -Tibilisi, 1961.
4. Jumaboyeva J. SH. O`zbekvaingliztillaridaleksikhamdastilistikgraduonimiya. Filol. fanl. dok. ... diss. avtoref. - Toshkent, 2016. - 82 b.;
5. Mahmudov N. Olamninglisoniymanzarasi vaso`zo`zlashtirish. Ozbek tili va adabiyoti. № 3. -Toshkent, 2015. -B. 7.
6. Musayev Q. Tarjimanazariyasiasoslari. -Toshkent, 2005. 14-16-b
7. Shoabdurahmonov Sh., Asqarova M., Xojiyev A. Hozirgi o`zbek adabiyati. - Toshkent: O`qituvchi. I qism, 1980.
8. Yuldasheva A. G. Idiomatik qo`shmaso`zlarning lingvokognitiv aspekti (ingliz-o`zbek tillarimisolida). Filol. fanl. bo`yichafals. dokt. (phd) diss. avtoref. - Toshkent, 2017. - 46 b.;
9. Z. Alimova. Alisher Navoiyning "Saddi Iskandariy" asaridagi ayrim forscha qo`shma so`zlarning leksik-semantik xususiyatlari haqida. Scientific journal of the Fergana State University. 2023, -P. 639-643.
10. Z. Alimova. Navoiyning "Saddi Iskandariy" asaridagi forscha-tojikcha so`zlarning semantik nihatdan guruhlanishi. Scientific journal of the Fergana State University. 2023, -P. 380-383.
11. Z. Alimova. Tillarda o`zlashma so`zlarning mavzuiy jihatdan guruhlanishi. Бюллетень педагогов нового Узбекистана. 2023, 1(4). 124-126.
12. AZ Vaxobovna. On Some Persian-Tajik Plant Names in Navoy's Epos" Saddi Iskandari". (2023) Texas Journal of Philology, Culture and History 18, 32-37.